

Description of Additional Supplementary Files

File Name: Supplementary Data 1

Description: Excel spreadsheets containing the numerical collection of the planet-generalized version N characterization factors for the 451 biosphere natural resource flows covered in the N flow database on tier 1 of the general framework of nitrogen flow accounting (GFNFA) under specific ecosystem N pools belonging.

File Name: Supplementary Data 2

Description: Excel spreadsheets containing the numerical collection of the planet-generalized version N characterization factors for the 3955 biosphere environmental emission flows covered in the N flow database on GFNFA tier 1 under specific ecosystem N pools belonging.

File Name: Supplementary Data 3

Description: Excel spreadsheets containing the numerical output during each time's Monte Carlo sampling of system carbon footprint, water footprint, reactive N input footprint, and reactive N output footprint under the baseline scenario.

File Name: Supplementary Data 4

Description: Excel spreadsheets containing each time of the Monte Carlo sampling's numerical output regarding the baseline scenario's inert N flow index, reactive N flow index, and N accumulation index on GFNFA tier 3.

File Name: Supplementary Data 5

Description: Excel spreadsheets containing detailed numerical data regarding the sensitivity of system carbon, water footprint, reactive N input and output footprint, and the ternary N flow sustainability indicators on GFNFA tier 3 to corresponding predominant life cycle parameters under the baseline scenario.

File Name: Supplementary Data 6

Description: Excel spreadsheets containing the detailed explanation of the N characterization factor data supporting the compilation of the planet-generalized N characterization factor for the corresponding natural resource flows, following Route D or E in Figure 12 of the manuscript.